

‘PERCEPTION OF STUDENTS OF TEACHER EDUCATION FOR SDG-3: GOOD HEALTH AND WELL-BEING

¹Shilpi Bhandari,

Research Scholar

²Prof. Seema Dhawan

Department of Education, HBNGU, Srinagar Garhwal

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Abstract

The environment and humans are interdependent. Without humans, the environment has no meaning and without the environment, human cannot imagine their existence on earth. This shows a direct relation between the both. But several human activities from the last few decades, on land, air, and water polluted the Environment. These all cause a huge loss of human lives and affect human health in terms of different communicable and non-communicable diseases. All these are constantly degrading human and environmental health. For good human and environmental health, everyone should be aware of holistic health and follow a healthy lifestyle. In this sense, the responsibility of Students of Teacher Education (STE) gets doubled in the sense that they prepare teachers, students, and citizens for their future regards. Therefore, it becomes necessary for STE to be aware of the term Sustainability and all SDGs, which ensures a sustainable livelihood for every individual. The objective of this study is to find out the perception of STE towards Sustainable Development Goal 3 - Good health and well-being. The sample comprises 113 STE (B.Ed. and M.Ed. students) of HNB Garhwal University, Srinagar. The quota sampling method has been taken to select the sample and Data has been collected through a self-developed questionnaire which consists of the items based on SDG-3. The present study will be helpful to train STE accordingly.

Keywords- Perception, SDG-3, Good Health and well-being, Students of Teacher Education (STE), Environment, Teacher Education.

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Introduction

“The climate crisis is a health crisis.”

By: - Maria Neira

Sustainable Development Goals adopted by UNESCO clarify the situation of the human race on the planet and aim to achieve by 2030. Because an individual is the single unit of a community, the goals aim for the betterment of the community through the betterment of an individual. The goals are mainly based on the theme ‘*No one should leave behind.*’ The theme was not in the concern of a single factor or component i.e., ‘Environment.’ The environment has a direct effect on human health. Roughly 24 percent of all global deaths are linked to the environment- a healthier environment could prevent these deaths (Health and the environment, 2022). So, A healthy environment is required for a healthy livelihood. We do not always see it, but our environment is shaping our health every moment of every day (Correll, 2020). But, Man’s activities in the environment have tended to degrade and make the environment untidy and unfit for human habitation because of its poor sanitation nature (Uchegbu, 2000). Because of several human activities, the atmospheric composition is changing day by day, which causes landslides, floods, climate change, global warming, etc. Whatever the circumstances are, we should also be aware of the present environmental situations and we must educate ourselves to be responsible for everything, which had gone wrong with the environment, we must educate ourselves to be accountable for our doings and to understand our relations to the environment. WHO defines health in terms of physical, mental, and social well-being. Not only in terms of the complete absence of any disease. This means health is not limited to the human body only. It has several other factors or components that are directly or indirectly related to human health and help to maintain a sustainable livelihood for humans and all living beings. To create a healthy environment for all under SDG:- 3, 9 targets settled to achieve the goals which target 3.1 state reduce maternal mortality rate, target 3.2 is, to end all preventable deaths under 5 years of age, target 3.3 is, to fight communicable diseases, target 3.4 is, reduce mortality from non-communicable diseases and promote mental-health, target 3.5 is, prevent and treat substance abuse, target 3.6 is, reduce road injuries and deaths (this target was the only target which was settled to be achieved in 2020), target 3.7 is, universal access to sexual and reproductive care, family planning and education, target 3.8 is, achieve universal health coverage and target 3.9 is, reduce illness and deaths from hazardous chemicals and pollution. These 9 targets cover all the areas that affect human health directly or indirectly. But still, it is well known that knowingly or unknowingly

humans are harming all the natural resources in the name of 'Development'. These natural resources are used by human for their livelihood and are also an essential component for healthy human life. This has led us to the present situation in which we started using the word '*Sustainable Development*' instead of '*Development*'. The term Sustainable But the question arises, Are the individuals familiar with the word '*Sustainable Development*'? So, the study focuses on finding out the perception of pupil-teacher educators towards Sustainable Development Goal- 3, Good health, and wellbeing. Who strengthens that society by introducing the values among them. Teachers should focus on teaching students the importance of the environment and allow them to realize the connections, patterns, and causes (Gamage, 2022). So, it becomes necessary for STE, to understand the environmental situations and how to tackle and overcome these situations. This research work will be significant in terms to aware STE of the concept of sustainable development, which help them to understand the true meaning of education and can develop a sense that '*No one should be left behind.*'

The young minds are the future and these minds are the decision makers of their own. This young generation can constitute the methods that are capable of training them to tackle the present problems. The researcher focuses on the demands of new methodology according to time which may be able to deal with the situations because the methods being used to solve the environmental problems are getting outdated. The researcher emphasizes on interdisciplinary exchange of research studies (Guegan, 2018). The environment, sanitation, and human health are interrelated. There is a strong relationship among them. Degradation in human health due to contaminated water and other natural resources, poor waste management, and uncleanliness and sanitation has a significant role in human habitation and must be improved human healthy lifestyle. Other global environmental problems also affect human health and lifestyle as well. There should be provision of safe drinking water for low-income groups, provision of health care services, construction of drains and sewers, etc. and the recruitment of sanitary inspector to re-enact the War Against Indiscipline (WAI) is also required (Uchegbu, 2015). So, everyone should be self-disciplined in terms of their health and lifestyle and this must be the priority for everyone and everyone should be aware of it. Keeping this in mind, the researcher decided to study the perception of pupil-teacher educators towards Sustainable Development Goal 3: Good Health and Wellbeing. A quantitative approach has been used for the study. The study was conducted on 43 pupil-teacher educators of the Birla campus of HNBGU, Srinagar Garhwal, Uttarakhand. For data collection, a Google form namely, '*Perception Tool for Sustainable Development Goal 3*' was formed. This tool

consisted of 24 multiple-choice type questions. The questions were mainly based on the indicators of 9 targets under the SDG: 3. Four options were given for each question, out of which only one option was correct. One mark was allotted for the correct option and zero for the wrong one. No negative marking was there. To know the level of perception of students, they were categorized into the following three levels based on the scores they obtained.

Table No.- 1: Categorization of STE

Scores	0-4	5-10	11-15	16-20	21-24
Level of Perception	Very Low	Low	Average	High	Very High

Result and Discussion

Table No.-2: Level of perception of STE for SDG 3

Category	Total	Level of perception				
		Very Low	Low	Average	High	Very High
Frequency	113	4	54	43	11	1
Percentage	100 per cent	4 per cent	48 per cent	38 per cent	10 per cent	1 per cent

Figure No.- 1

Table No.-2 shows that out of 113 students, 4(4 percent) students were found in the category of very low level of perception, 54(48 percent) students were in the category of low level of perception, 43(38 percent) students were in the category of Average level of perception while 11(10 percent) students were in the category of High level of perception and only 1(1 per cent) were in the category of Very high level of perception.

Table No.-3: Perception of Female and Male STE

GENDER	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	Sig.
FEMALE	60	11.25	3.943	1.752	Non-Sig.
MALE	53	10.06	3.201		

Table no.- 3 shows that the mean of female and male students was 11.25 and 10.06 respectively. The standard deviation of female and male students was found as 3.943 and 3.201. The degree of freedom was 111. t-value for female and male students is calculated as 1.752, which is less than the Table value. Based on this the null hypothesis previously formulated was failed to reject and no significant difference in the perception of first- and second-year students for SDG -3, Good health, and well-being was found.

Table No.-4: Perception of B.Ed. and M.Ed. students

COURSE	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	Sig.
B.Ed.	58	10.41	3.174	0.826	Non-Sig.
M.Ed.	55	14.98	4.098		

df-111

Table no.- 4 shows that the mean of B.Ed. and M.Ed. students was 10.41 and 14.98 respectively. The standard deviation of B.Ed. and M.Ed. students was found as 3.174 and 4.098. The degree of freedom was 111. t-value for B.Ed. and M.Ed. students is calculated as 0.826, which is less than the Table value. Based on this the null hypothesis previously formulated was failed to reject and no significant difference in the perception of B.Ed. and M.Ed. students for the SDG- 3, Good health and well-being was found.

Table No.-5: Perception of Science and Art stream STE

STREAM	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	Sig.
SCIENCE	56	11.38	3.850	2.004	0.01
ART	57	10.02	3.829		

df-111

Figure No.- 2

Table no.- 5 shows that the mean of female and male students was 11.38 and 10.02 respectively. The standard deviation of female and male students was found as 3.850 and 3.829. The degree of freedom was 111. t-value for science and art stream students is calculated as 2.004, which is greater than the Table value. Based on this the null hypothesis previously formulated was rejected and a significant difference in the perception of first- and second-year students for SDG- 3, Good health and well-being was found.

Table No.-6: Perception of Hindi and English medium STE

MEDIUM	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	Sig.
HINDI	71	9.68	3.264	4.106	0.01
ENGLISH	42	12.40	3.656		

df-111

Figure No.- 3

Table no.- 6 shows that the mean of Hindi medium and English medium students was 9.68 and 12.4 respectively. The standard deviation of Hindi medium and English medium was found as 3.264 and 3.656. The degree of freedom was 111. t-value for Hindi and English medium students is calculated as 4.106, which is greater than the Table value. Based on this the null hypothesis previously formulated was rejected and a significant difference in the perception of Hindi and English medium STE for SDG- 3, Good health and well-being was found.

Discussion and Conclusion: By comparing the means of science and art stream STE it is found that science stream STE has a greater mean in comparison to art stream STE. This shows a significant difference between the both. This difference may be because of the science stream STE may be familiar with the concepts related to human health like environment, drugs, medicines, nutrition, diet, disasters, effects of chemicals on human health, effects of environmental issues on human health, and several others factors those have a direct or indirect

influence on human health. While art stream STE generally engaged with their traditional studies. So, it becomes necessary that students of the art stream should be taught the concepts related to human health and the factors that directly or indirectly affect human health. On comparing the perception of Hindi and English medium STE, the result also shows that the mean of English medium STE is greater than the mean of Hindi medium students. This may be because the availability of the literature related to sustainable development goals in the Hindi language is not quite enough. English is an international language but there are more than 7000 languages in the world spoken by peoples of different regions of different countries and there are many peoples who understands and speaks Hindi language. Also, there are some people who do not understand or are not familiar with the English language. So, it may be possible because of the reason, students were unable to understand the concept of SDGs and are not familiar with SDG-3. So, the literature should be available in both languages and the literature should be available or translated in maximum languages so that everyone can make them capable of understanding the concept of SDGs and direct their actions toward achieving sustainability.

The study shows that STE has less information about Sustainable Development Goal 3: Good Health and Well-Being, which ensures a healthy lifestyle for humans of all age groups. As previously discussed, table no.- 2 shows that only 10 percent of STE are in a high level of perception and only 1 percent of STE are in a very high level of perception while 48 percent of STE were in a low level of perception, which is the greatest percentage among all and 4 percent STE were in a very low level of perception. While the perception of STE should be high or very high. We must be aware of our health. As Aristotle also defines education as, *'Education is the creation of a sound mind in a sound body.'* Naturalism also focuses on physical development in the first five years of human age. So that it becomes a necessary component of our education that everyone should be aware of their health, especially in the present scenario, when environmental issues are going to be one of the major problems for all living organisms day by day. So, the concept of sustainability ensures not only a healthy lifestyle for all but also sensitizes everyone towards their surroundings. Sustainable Development Goal: 3 focuses on human health, mental health, and environmental health. Human health is directly related to the environment as target 3.9 states that 'Reduce illness and deaths from hazardous chemicals and pollution,' which can be achieved by means of reducing the mortality rate from air pollution and unsafe water sanitation, mentioned as the indicators to achieve the target. So, STE should have the information about Goal: 3. Because if, a teacher educator bears

the knowledge about these targets and indicators they will be able to convey the information easily to the teachers, and teachers are concerned as the source of knowledge, who transfer their knowledge to their learner effectively, either in concrete or in abstract form. Teachers are in direct contact with their students so; a teacher can better help their students to prepare themselves according to the present situations of the world. Teachers will aware their learners for their health and tell them the importance of sanitation and hygiene. As a teacher, our main aim is to make students learn effectively and efficiently (Singh, 2012). But the Teachers' educators prepare our teachers & the target year to achieve the goals is not too far. So, it becomes necessary that STE should have enough information about the target. SDGs are not related to a single issue but they include all the issues related to a single person to global issues. To resolve the issues, knowing is the leading step to the solution of a problem. So, the responsibility of STE doubles in the sense that they are on a heavy-duty to prepare a community of well-knowledgeable, skilled, and aware teachers and citizens towards the environment and health. As a result, everyone will be able to understand, 'If the human is healthy the community will already be wealthy.' We need to strengthen student abilities or skills by using teachers as facilitators in schools (Reddy, 2019). So that the information and skills of STE directly or indirectly affect students learning in different areas. That is why we need to strengthen the abilities or skills of STE first, only then can prepare their learner better.

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